

Spectrophotometric Studies of Alizarin Sulphonate and Ti (III) Complex

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Alizarin sodium sulphonate forms coloured complex with several rare earths viz., Y, La, Pr, Nd, Gd and Eu as reported by Rinchart¹. The complexes of Th, Na, Mo, Al, Cu and Indium²⁻⁷ have been reported in the literature.

Ti (III), chloride gives a red colour complex with Alizarin sulphonate in aqueous solution. In the present work the complex was not isolated but was studied in solution. The metal ligand ratio was found out by various methods using spectrophotometry.

EXPERIMENTAL

TiCl₃ was purified by crystallizing by a method described in Mellor⁸. The crystals were dried up under vacuum and covered with toluene layer, stored in dark and in an inert atmosphere to check oxidation.

The stock solution of TiCl₃ was prepared in air free double distilled conductivity water, covered with kerosene oil. This solution was standardised by adding a known volume of it in excess of pure ferric alum solution, containing sulphuric acid and titrating the resulting FeSO₄ against the standard KMnO₄ solution.

Determination of Metal Ligand ratio : Spectronic-20 Bausch and Lomb spectrophotometer was used. Vosburgh and Cooper method⁹ shows the formation of a single complex and has been further supported by Job's method¹⁰ of continuous variations, slope ratio method¹¹ and molar ratio method¹².

DISCUSSION

Vosburgh and Cooper method bears the testimony to the formation of a single complex under the usual conditions of colorimetric analysis in aqueous medium and also show that the maximum absorption occurs at 430 m μ , Job's method of continuous variations indicate a molar ratio of 1 : 1 for the metal and the ligand. The ratio is the same for its complex with many trivalent ions as Sc, Y, Al.

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